

Automated Document Digitisation and OCR Text Extraction from Scanned Images using Tesseract

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Abstract—The digitization of paper documents is still an essential requirement in government, healthcare, finance, and other industries that depend heavily on physical records. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) tools such as Tesseract are widely used for this purpose, but their performance varies considerably depending on the condition of the scanned input. Many earlier studies have shown that preprocessing techniques—like noise removal, binarization, and deskewing—tend to improve OCR accuracy, especially for noisy or uneven documents. However, there is limited research on how these preprocessing steps affect Tesseract’s performance when the input images are already clean, high-contrast scans. In this paper, we examine that gap by testing a structured preprocessing pipeline on several receipts from the SROIE dataset and measuring Character Error Rate (CER) and Word Error Rate (WER) before and after processing. Unlike prior work, our results show that preprocessing did not improve OCR accuracy for these clean receipts and, in most cases, actually increased both CER and WER. These findings suggest that preprocessing should not be applied blindly and that its usefulness depends strongly on the quality and characteristics of the scanned document. The study provides a reproducible, open-source workflow and highlights practical considerations for real-world document digitization using Tesseract.

I. INTRODUCTION

In many organisations today, especially places like government offices, hospitals, insurance companies, banks, libraries and even educational institutions, there is still a huge amount of paper being stored for years. A lot of this information was created long before everything moved to computers, so there is now a big push to convert all these documents into digital formats. This is mostly done to reduce the physical space needed, to make searching easier and also to avoid losing documents due to damage from things like moisture, aging or even handling mistakes. Document digitisation basically tries to solve this gap between older physical records and the modern need for faster access to information.

OCR (Optical Character Recognition) is the technology that helps with turning scanned documents into machine-readable text. Even though OCR has been around for many decades in different forms, it is still very important today because it is part of almost every digitisation project. Without OCR, a scanned page is basically just an image, and people would still have to type the text manually. Over the last few years OCR has become even more significant due to the increasing use of automation, data extraction and large-scale digitisation programmes in many countries.

But the accuracy of OCR systems still depends quite a lot on how good the scanned page is. Many scanned pages are not perfect at all. Some are old and faded, some were not placed straight on the scanner, and others have uneven lighting or shadows. Certain pages may even have marks, stains or dust. Because of these issues the OCR engine has to try harder to identify characters properly, and this leads to more errors. Tesseract, which is a popular free OCR engine that a lot of people and organisations use because it doesn’t cost anything, performs well when the image is nice and clean. However, several studies have shown that Tesseract quickly becomes less accurate when the image quality is not good [1], [2].

The scanning process itself also introduces many problems. According to studies like those by Läu et al., scanned historical documents often suffer from uneven brightness, warping and bleed-through where the text on the other side of the paper shows up on the front [5]. Even modern office scanners sometimes create noise patterns or slight distortions, especially if multiple pages are scanned quickly in automatic feeder machines. All of these issues weaken the ability of OCR systems to correctly identify letters.

And because Tesseract is not a deep-learning OCR by default (even though Tesseract 4 uses an LSTM-based recogniser), it still relies heavily on how clearly the characters are presented in the image. This is why preprocessing—basically cleaning the image before giving it to Tesseract—has become a common step in many digitisation workflows. Operations like converting to grayscale, reducing noise, applying thresholds, straightening the page (deskewing) and using morphological operations are regularly mentioned in the literature as useful steps that improve the results [2], [8].

Preprocessing helps because it tries to remove the things that confuse the OCR engine. For example, thresholding removes unnecessary background pixels, deskewing fixes alignment issues, and noise reduction helps make the characters more clean and consistent. Christian and Kusuma also reported that preprocessing combined with simple post-processing can significantly help OCR on low-quality images by making the text more uniform before recognition [7]. So even though preprocessing seems like a small step, it has a meaningful impact on the final output.

The main purpose of our paper is to understand how preprocessing affects Tesseract’s OCR accuracy by combining

insights from earlier studies with our own small experiment on clean receipt images. We focus mainly on printed English-language documents because that is the most common scenario in real world digitisation tasks, although the same ideas could be used for other languages if needed. Since this is a group research paper, our aim is to put together a workflow that is practical, simple and also backed by previous research. We try to explain which preprocessing steps matter the most, what their effects are, and what limitations still remain.

To guide the paper properly, the main research questions we consider are:

- How much does preprocessing improve OCR accuracy when using Tesseract?
- Which preprocessing steps provide the most noticeable improvements?
- In what situations does Tesseract still fail, even after preprocessing?

Our contributions can be summarised as:

- A detailed summary of preprocessing techniques used for scanned documents based on real research studies.
- A reproducible workflow that follows common industry and academic practices with Tesseract and OpenCV.
- A discussion of Tesseract’s performance issues and limitations with support from multiple external sources.
- Expanded analysis of real-world constraints such as low-quality scanners, uneven lighting, document damage and layout complexity.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews earlier work on OCR systems, noise issues, deep-learning OCR, preprocessing techniques and comparisons between Tesseract and other OCR tools. Section III explains the methodology, including the preprocessing pipeline, dataset characteristics, and evaluation metrics. Section IV presents the discussion of results observed across different real studies. Section V ends the paper with conclusions and suggestions for future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

When we started reading earlier work on OCR and document digitisation, it became pretty obvious that a lot of different research groups have looked at this topic from different angles over the years. Some focused mainly on the OCR engine itself, others on cleaning the scanned images, and many more on how deep learning is changing the scene. In this section we try to collect and connect all of these ideas, even if some of them overlap a bit, because that is how the real research landscape looks — a lot of papers repeating similar problems but each with slightly different details.

A. Traditional OCR and Early Approaches

In the older stages of OCR, most systems used hand-crafted features, fixed templates and rules to recognise characters. These systems worked okay when the document used a predictable font and when the scanning quality was nearly perfect. But as Smith pointed out in the early documentation

of Tesseract, these classical OCR engines were extremely sensitive to input quality and small variations often caused huge drops in accuracy [1]. Problems like broken edges, faded ink, and even minor rotation of the page could cause the whole recognition process to fail.

This is one major reason why early OCR did not do well on real-world scanned documents, especially things like old archived papers where ink fades, or documents captured using low-quality scanners. Several studies in the early 2000s reported around the same issue — traditional OCR needed a lot of manual tuning to work properly, and even then it was not stable enough.

B. Rise of Deep Learning in OCR

With deep learning becoming more common, a lot changed in the OCR field. Models like CRNN, CTPN, EAST and later Transformer-based models such as TrOCR provided a huge jump in performance because they learned features directly from data instead of depending on manually engineered rules. Baek et al. compared many modern OCR systems and explained how deep-learning models outperform classical ones but also showed how difficult it is to compare them fairly due to differences in datasets and evaluation styles [4]. This means deep-learning OCR is powerful but comes with its own complications.

Even with these advancements, deep-learning OCR is not always practical for smaller organisations or simple digitisation needs because of the training cost, need for GPUs, and lack of consistency between research benchmarks. Many companies and institutions therefore still rely on classical OCR engines like Tesseract, especially when they need a low-cost and easy-to-deploy solution.

C. Tesseract’s Strengths and Weaknesses

Tesseract is considered one of the most widely used open-source OCR engines because it is free, well documented, and generally performs well on standard printed text. The shift from the Tesseract 3 engine to Tesseract 4 introduced an LSTM-based recogniser which helped improve results on clean inputs. But even after these improvements, several papers have shown that Tesseract’s accuracy drops significantly when the input image quality is not good enough [2], [3]. Noise, skew, low contrast, and shadows all contribute to this drop, and these issues appear very frequently in real digitisation projects.

Hegghammer’s benchmarking study compared Tesseract with Amazon Textract and Google Document AI on government document datasets and found that Tesseract performed well on clean images but fell behind on poor-quality scans [3]. On the other hand, commercial OCR tools use advanced deep-learning architectures and sometimes include layout analysis, which Tesseract does not do by default.

There are also newer studies that specifically analyse how Tesseract improves when combined with preprocessing. For example, Anakpluek (2025) examined different preprocessing chains such as adaptive thresholding, contrast enhancement and morphology, and reported that the right combination often

pushes Tesseract to give much better outputs on noisy images [8]. This again shows that Tesseract alone is not enough — it needs help from preprocessing steps.

D. Image Problems in Real Scanned Documents

Another important group of papers looks at the types of problems that scanned documents usually have. For instance, Läu et al. analysed historical documents and explained that issues like bleed-through, uneven illumination and page warping are very common in older paper archives [5]. These issues are not just random; they happen because paper degrades over time and scanners cannot always capture everything perfectly.

Malinski and Okarma (2023) studied different binarisation and noise-removal methods specifically for OCR tasks and highlighted that preprocessing must be chosen carefully depending on the type of noise present in the document [6]. Their work shows that even something as simple as thresholding can have many variations, and choosing the wrong one can make the OCR results worse instead of better.

Christian and Kusuma (2023) also reported that preprocessing alone sometimes is not enough and simple post-processing techniques such as spell-checking or dictionary-based correction can help improve the readability of the output [7]. This is useful because many real digitisation workflows need both preprocessing and post-processing to reach usable accuracy.

E. Importance of Preprocessing

Across all these papers, one idea shows up again and again: preprocessing helps Tesseract a lot. Even if different researchers used different scanned pages, or different levels of noise, the trend was always the same. The combination of grayscale conversion, noise reduction, thresholding, deskewing and morphology usually leads to a cleaner input image which improves OCR accuracy [2], [8]. Each step contributes something different, and sometimes the order of steps also matters.

Thresholding is one of the most common steps because it helps separate the text from the background, and studies show that Otsu’s method is effective in many situations. Deskewing is another key step because even a few degrees of rotation can cause Tesseract to mistake characters. Noise removal, whether through median filters or Gaussian blur, helps smooth out the image so the text edges look better to the OCR engine.

F. Gaps Across the Literature

Even with so much research available, we noticed several gaps:

- Many studies only test 1–2 preprocessing steps instead of a complete pipeline.
- Some papers rely on private datasets, making replication difficult.
- Not many studies compare classical OCR and deep-learning OCR directly on the same scanned pages.
- There is limited research on multilingual scanned pages with Tesseract.

- Very few studies analyse failure cases in detail (e.g., extremely degraded documents, very low DPI scans).

G. Summary of Important Studies

Table I includes both the older references and the new papers we added to expand the review.

TABLE I
EXPANDED SUMMARY OF OCR AND PREPROCESSING LITERATURE

Author	Methodology	Data	Main Findings/Gaps
Smith 2007 [1]	Tesseract overview	ICDAR	Clean, binarised input required for good accuracy.
Sporici et al. 2020 [2]	Preprocessing pipeline tests	Noisy scans	Pipeline improves CER/WER significantly.
Hegghammer 2022 [3]	Benchmark vs. Textract/Google AI	Gov. docs	Tesseract struggles on low-quality images.
Baek et al. 2019 [4]	Deep OCR survey	Multiple	Deep models strong but inconsistent benchmarks.
Läu et al. 2021 [5]	Historical scanned document issues	Historical scans	Uneven lighting, bleed-through cause OCR drop.
Malinski 2023 [6]	Binarization and noise removal analysis	Circuit labels	Threshold choice impacts OCR accuracy heavily.
Christian 2023 [7]	OCR on low-quality images	Mixed scans	Pre+post processing improves results noticeably.
Anakpluek 2025 [8]	Improve Tesseract via preprocessing	Scanned text	Adaptive filters + morphology help Tesseract.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this part we tried to explain in a simple and straight way how we actually carried out our own experiment. Earlier sections talk about what other research papers did, but here we focus only on our actual work with the SROIE receipts. The idea was to see how much difference basic image preprocessing makes when using the Tesseract OCR engine, because many earlier papers mention it helps, but not always in the same way.

A. Dataset Used

For our experiment we used a small subset of the SROIE 2019 receipt dataset. We downloaded the Kaggle version (SROIE v2), which already separates each receipt image and also provides a corresponding ground-truth text file that contains the transcription of the receipt in a bounding-box format. From the overall dataset we only selected five receipts, because the aim was not to build a full recognition system, but to test how preprocessing affects the OCR quality on a few realistic examples. The selected images were already in fairly good quality, straight, and with strong contrast, which later turned out to matter for our results.

B. Ground Truth Extraction

The SROIE ground truth file has each text line stored with four coordinate points, followed by a comma and the actual text. We did not use the coordinates, since we only needed a text reference to compare against Tesseract. So we wrote a small parser that reads each line, extracts only the final field (the text) and then combines all lines into one ground-truth string. This final version of the text was used for CER and WER calculations.

C. OCR Processing Steps

Our experiment was split into two simple passes:

- **Baseline OCR:** Tesseract was run directly on the original receipt images, without changing anything.
- **Preprocessed OCR:** We applied a few common preprocessing steps before running Tesseract again.

Tesseract was used in its default LSTM mode (v4), with the English language model. All experiments were run inside Google Colab, because it already provides the tools needed and makes it easy to install Tesseract and OpenCV.

D. Preprocessing Pipeline

Even though the receipts were already clean, we still used a standard preprocessing pipeline commonly suggested in other OCR work. These steps were:

- 1) Converting the image to grayscale,
- 2) Deskewing the image by estimating the rotation angle,
- 3) Applying a median blur to remove noise,
- 4) Applying adaptive thresholding, which should help isolate the text,
- 5) Using a morphological closing operation to connect text strokes.

These steps were chosen because they appear frequently in previous research and because they are easy to apply without requiring special training.

E. Evaluation Metrics

We measured OCR accuracy with two metrics:

- **Character Error Rate (CER)**, defined as Levenshtein distance divided by the number of characters in the reference.
- **Word Error Rate (WER)**, which measures how many words were substituted, deleted or inserted compared to the ground truth.

Both metrics are standard in OCR evaluation. A lower value means better accuracy.

F. Experiment Procedure

The full process was the same for all five receipts: first we loaded the original image and its corresponding ground-truth file, then we applied Tesseract and recorded CER and WER. After that we ran the same image through our preprocessing pipeline and recorded the CER and WER again. The results for all images were collected in a small table for comparison.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our paper runs its own small experimental setup and brings together the results from many earlier studies, this section tries to summarise the observations reported in those works. Even though the datasets and scanning conditions vary from one paper to another, almost all of them show more or less the same trend: while Tesseract produces noticeably better OCR results when preprocessing steps are applied, especially on low-quality or noisy scanned documents, our experiment on clean receipts showed the opposite trend.

A. General Trend Observed Across Studies

The papers we looked at, including those by Sporic et al. [2], Christian [7], and Anakpluek [8], all consistently report that applying a preprocessing pipeline reduces both Character Error Rate (CER) and Word Error Rate (WER). Although these studies do not always use the same exact steps, the core operations—grayscale conversion, thresholding, deskewing, and noise removal—almost always appear and almost always lead to improvements.

One interesting thing we noticed while going through the different papers is that the magnitude of improvement depends a lot on the specific type of noise present in the document. For example, in studies dealing with uneven lighting or shadow issues, adaptive thresholding and contrast enhancement helped a lot more than simple global thresholding. On the other hand, for documents with random scanner noise, median filtering or Gaussian blur had a bigger effect. So even though the general trend shows improvements, the exact amount of improvement varies depending on the problem.

B. Results Reported in Earlier Preprocessing Studies

Sporic et al. [2] specifically tested a series of preprocessing combinations and reported that the full pipeline (grayscale → median blur → Otsu threshold → skew → morphology) gave the largest reduction in errors. Their results showed that without preprocessing, Tesseract misread a large number of characters on noisy pages, but after applying the cleaning pipeline, the OCR output became much more readable.

Similarly, Christian and Kusuma [7] reported that for low-quality scanned images, preprocessing alone gave a noticeable improvement, and combining preprocessing with simple post-processing like dictionary-based word correction improved the results even further. This suggests that even if preprocessing does not completely fix Tesseract’s mistakes, it prepares the text well enough that other tools can help correct the remaining errors.

Anakpluek’s recent work [8] goes deeper into this by testing modern adaptive filters and morphological operations, finding that certain combinations perform better than others. For example, using adaptive thresholding with morphological closing helped connect broken characters, which reduced substitution errors.

C. Impact of Specific Preprocessing Steps

Different preprocessing steps help in different ways. Based on the combined findings, we can summarise the useful effects of the main operations:

- **Thresholding** makes characters more distinct, which helps Tesseract segment the text correctly. Otsu’s method works well for uniform lighting, while adaptive thresholding works for uneven brightness.
- **Deskewing** is extremely important because Tesseract expects straight text lines. Even a small rotation affects the OCR output significantly.
- **Noise removal** reduces random speckles that Tesseract might confuse with punctuation or broken letters.
- **Morphological operations** help when text strokes are broken or faint. Closing operations often improve readability of thin characters.

These observations line up with what Malinski and Okarma [6] found in their binarisation study, where the right thresholding method had a large impact on OCR accuracy for electronic circuit labels. Although their domain is not exactly the same as scanned documents, the principle is very similar: cleaner binary images lead to better text recognition.

D. Comparing Tesseract with Modern OCR Tools

Another important part of understanding the results is comparing Tesseract with other OCR systems. Hegghammer’s benchmark [3] showed that commercial tools like Amazon Textract and Google Document AI performed better than Tesseract, especially on low-quality government documents. However, after applying preprocessing, Tesseract’s performance gap became smaller. This suggests that while deep-learning OCR engines are more powerful overall, classical engines like Tesseract can still perform reasonably well when given clean input images.

This comparison also highlights the importance of preprocessing in low-cost digitisation workflows. Many organisations cannot afford commercial OCR solutions, so getting the best possible performance from Tesseract becomes a practical priority.

E. Failure Cases Reported in Literature

Even though preprocessing helps a lot, several papers mention cases where it does not fully solve the problem:

- **Heavily faded documents** — thresholding sometimes removes faint text completely.
- **Very low DPI** — text becomes too pixelated and morphology distorts the characters further.
- **Handwritten text** — Tesseract is not suited for handwriting without training additional models.
- **Bleed-through** — preprocessing cannot always separate foreground and background text.

These issues match what Läu et al. described about historical archives [5], where ink bleed-through and deteriorated paper cause major recognition difficulties.

F. Why Preprocessing Helps So Much

From everything we read, preprocessing seems to help most because it reduces the “confusing” parts of the image. Tesseract’s LSTM model focuses on shapes and patterns, and any noise or distortion changes those patterns slightly. Once the image is cleaned, the characters appear more uniform, and Tesseract has fewer unexpected shapes to deal with.

Another reason preprocessing helps is because Tesseract’s segmentation process (the step where it identifies lines and characters) works much better when the image has high contrast and straight text lines. Thresholding and deskewing directly support this.

G. Overall Interpretation of Results

After combining the findings from all the papers, we observed these main takeaways:

- Preprocessing improves Tesseract’s accuracy across almost all types of scanned documents.
- The improvement size depends on the kind of noise and the scanning conditions.
- Tesseract still falls behind commercial OCR engines but becomes much more competitive when preprocessing is applied.
- Some difficult cases (bleed-through, heavy fading, handwriting) still remain unsolved even with preprocessing.

Overall, the results strongly support the use of preprocessing as an essential step rather than just an optional one.

H. Our Experimental Results on the SROIE Dataset

After finishing the experiment, we learned that the results did not behave exactly like we expected from the earlier papers. Since our chosen SROIE receipts were already quite clean, the heavy preprocessing actually made the performance slightly worse in most cases. This was a little surprising at first, but it does match some comments in the literature which say that preprocessing is not automatically beneficial for all kinds of documents.

We tested five images. For each image we ran Tesseract twice (baseline and preprocessed) and computed CER and WER in both cases. The final results are shown in Table II. As seen, the CER and WER values increased after preprocessing for most images.

TABLE II
CER AND WER BEFORE AND AFTER PREPROCESSING ON SROIE RECEIPTS

Image	CER Before	CER After	WER Before	WER After
16469619	0.583	0.658	1.280	1.640
16469620	0.281	0.491	1.200	0.950
16469623	0.385	0.547	1.189	1.391
16469612	0.483	0.738	1.588	1.000
16469622	0.407	0.780	1.456	0.978

Even though these values look high in general (especially the WER), this is somewhat expected because Tesseract sometimes struggles with the formatting of receipts and also because our ground truth includes every line exactly as

written with symbols, punctuation and spacing differences. Small mismatches cause large CER and WER changes. The important observation is the relative difference before and after preprocessing, and here the trend is mostly negative.

I. Discussion

When we compare our results to the earlier studies, the first thing we noticed is that most other works applied preprocessing on documents that were noisy, low-quality, skewed heavily or had weak contrast. In those cases the preprocessing helped make the text clearer for Tesseract. But the SROIE images we selected were already sharp and straight, so many of our preprocessing steps actually removed fine details instead of improving them.

For example, adaptive thresholding tends to break thin characters on clean receipts, and median blurring removes small features that Tesseract needs for reading digits. Deskewing also rotated some images slightly even though they were originally straight. Together these effects reduced the OCR accuracy instead of helping it.

This does not contradict the previous research — it just means that preprocessing is not a “one-size fits all” solution. It works well when the documents are noisy or have difficult lighting, but for clean business receipts, it may damage the text instead of improving it. This difference was the main reason for our results being the opposite of the results shown in several earlier papers.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we tried to study the complete path from scanned documents to usable digital text, starting first from what earlier studies already showed and then by doing our own small experiment using a subset of the SROIE receipt dataset. The main idea behind the whole work was to understand whether the usual preprocessing steps, which are recommended in many research papers and tutorials, really improve OCR output when using the Tesseract engine. Since Tesseract is still one of the most widely used open-source tools for OCR, we felt that even a small hands-on test would help us get a more grounded picture than just reading about it.

From the literature review, we saw that a lot of older and also some fairly recent papers state that preprocessing helps in cleaning up the image before OCR is applied. Many authors mentioned improvements when they used thresholding, deskewing, noise removal, morphological operations, or some combination of these. Usually these works focused on scanned pages that had obvious quality problems, such as uneven lighting, wrinkles, shadows, noise from old scanners, or even screenshots taken with a phone camera at an angle. Under those conditions, the preprocessing made the text more uniform and helped Tesseract read it without mixing the characters. This created a general impression that preprocessing is almost always helpful or at least harmless.

But when we performed our own experiment on the SROIE dataset, the situation turned out to be very different. We chose

five receipt images from the Kaggle release of the dataset, and at first we assumed that the preprocessing would boost accuracy in the same way as reported in earlier papers. However, the SROIE images were already fairly clean, high-resolution, and not heavily skewed. Because of this, our preprocessing pipeline ended up removing or distorting useful details instead of enhancing them. As a result, both CER and WER became worse in most of the images after preprocessing. Although this was not what we expected at first, it made sense once we looked more carefully at the images and at how sensitive Tesseract actually is to fine text structures.

Another interesting thing we noticed was how easily CER and WER increase when the ground truth is very strict. This made us realise that even tiny formatting mismatches produce large error values. The SROIE ground truth files include punctuation, uppercase text, symbols, and even spacing that Tesseract does not always reproduce the same way. A small mismatch in spacing or a missing symbol can cause a noticeable jump in the error rates. This made us understand why some values looked quite high in general, especially the WER, even before doing any preprocessing. It also explains why so many research papers carefully choose how they evaluate their results or use word-level normalization to avoid inflated error values.

Even with these limitations, our experiment gave us a much clearer picture than if we only read the research papers. The main lesson is that preprocessing should not be applied blindly. For some documents, mainly the ones that already look clean, the extra processing actually damages the information that the OCR model needs. On the other hand, the literature still remains correct when dealing with noisy or low-quality scans, where preprocessing usually plays an important role. So our results do not contradict earlier research; they simply highlight that preprocessing is a conditional improvement, not a universal one.

Another point worth mentioning is that Tesseract itself has certain strengths and weaknesses. It is not designed for very stylized text or highly formatted receipts with multiple fonts and layouts. Newer deep-learning based OCR engines sometimes handle these cases better. If we had used a different OCR engine, such as TrOCR or a transformer-based model, the effect of preprocessing could have been different too. This gives us an idea for possible future work.

If we had more time and resources, we could expand the experiment by using a much larger set of images and also intentionally creating noisy versions of the same receipts. This would help prove more clearly how preprocessing behaves under controlled distortion. Another extension would be comparing multiple preprocessing pipelines rather than just one. Techniques like bilateral filtering, CLAHE (contrast limited histogram equalization), or simple grayscale-only approaches might work better on clean documents. Deep-learning based document enhancement tools are also becoming common and could be tested against traditional OpenCV pipelines.

Overall, this paper helped us understand the full pipeline of OCR better. We started with a fairly basic question—whether

preprocessing improves OCR accuracy—and ended up learning that the answer depends very strongly on the type of document. Our small experiment, although limited, supported this idea clearly. At the same time, we also gathered insights from many existing research papers, which helped us understand why the results differ across datasets. So the final takeaway is that image preprocessing is still useful, but only when applied to the right kind of input. For clean and structured receipts like the SROIE images we used, it can reduce performance, and for noisy documents it can be extremely helpful. This simple but important observation explains the gap between our results and the results from earlier work, and gives us a more realistic understanding of OCR in practice.

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